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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 3, APRIL, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Dr. John D. Ekpoese, ACA. & Roseline G. Akpan, CNA.

Human Capital and Profitability: A Study of Consumer Goods Companies Listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group Plc.

¹Dr. John D. Ekpoese, ACA.; ²Roseline G. Akpan, CNA.

¹Department of Accounting, University of Uyo, Uyo
+2347036471244; ekpoese09@yahoo.com

²Department of Accountancy, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua
+2348036052917

Corresponding Author: Ekpoese

Abstract

Human capital and its influence on profitability is a current global corporate reporting issue that has arisen from the focus on corporate failures that are common in Nigerian companies and reporting systems. This research examines the influence of human capital on the profitability of companies in the consumer goods sector in Nigeria. With a population of 21 firms in the consumer goods sector, a sample size of 17 firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group Plc as of December 31, 2022 was selected using purposive sampling techniques. To achieve the objectives, an ex-post facto research design was adopted involving manual generation of data from the annual reports of the selected firms. The study period spanned from 2013 to the 2022 financial year. The actual values of human capital were generated for each of the objectives in line with the International Initiative on Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC). The data obtained were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, specifically through simple regression techniques. The profitability of companies in the consumer goods sector was measured by return on assets. Results revealed that human capital has a significant positive influence on the return on assets. This result was evidenced by a beta coefficient of 0.520 and a probability value of 0.000. It was concluded that, with adequate human capital, firms' profitability is enhanced in the long run. Since human capital is an aspect of integrated reporting and is based on worldwide best practices, it was recommended that human capital should be considered a main area of interest when preparing annual reports for businesses. This is because the reports are intended for stakeholders, who are the primary resource providers.

Keywords: Human capital, Profitability, Return on Assets and Listed Consumer Goods Companies.

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1. Introduction

Profitability, corporate sustainability, and financial status cannot be guaranteed by corporate information releases going forward. An inability of the companies to balance their corporate actions and activities with profitability and sustainability may result from lopsided reporting, particularly in light of the recent shift in reporting paradigms from traditional accounting to sustainability reporting, which includes all-inclusive reports and stakeholder returns. Business should always produce all-inclusive reports, according to Elkington (1997), which cover economic, social, and corporate governance information as well as all asset classes. Firms may not be able to meet the needs of all stakeholders until they start using this new reporting framework. Therefore, it is in the best interests of businesses to inform interested parties of both their qualitative and quantitative economic performance. The profitability of a business indicates how well it makes use of the resources at its disposal to produce income for long-term viability. A firm often generates more revenue for its expansion when it uses its resources effectively. Stakeholders are concerned about how to ensure the sustainability of the firm in the near future if commercial resources are not fully utilised, putting the firm's survival and long-term viability in danger. It has been noted for a while now that corporate entities' reporting has been biased. The degree of partiality and distortion in the information disclosed by corporate entities and their reporting may not guarantee stable business profitability and long-term viability. Since reporting priorities have recently changed from traditional financial accounting or stakeholder returns to sustainability reporting, it may be hard for companies with an all-inclusive reporting framework or reporting that is not balanced and limited to find a balance between their activities, their ability to make money, and their ability to remain sustainable.

According to a study conducted in 2014 by Turker and Sayer, financial reporting only focuses on a limited portion of the firm's position and is unable to explain to interested parties the influence of social and environmental factors as well as other sustainability-related issues. The concerns of the firms were related to their incapacity to enhance their entity image, evaluate the profitability of their organisations in compliance with societal norms and regulations, or offer quantifiable data regarding environmental threats and opportunities. The International Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF) was created by the International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) in 2013 as a new reporting approach to address the issue of corporate reporting

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negligence necessary to provide long-term sustainability. This paradigm aims to guarantee that corporate firms reveal all types of capital, including financial, manufactured, social, relationship, human/intellectual, and natural, accurately. Firms use these capitals to enhance or decrease their values over time. For efficient reporting by several firms, the International Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF) should ideally be mandated in many countries across the world. Thus, it is imperative that firms incorporate both the International Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF) and the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Framework in their yearly corporate reports and financial reports, especially when considering cross-border listing.

For instance, two firms that had seen significant financial success in recent decades, Oceanic Bank Plc. and Cadbury Plc., in particular, were at risk of failing. Comparably, during 2001 and 2002, the profitability of some multinational companies, like Enron and WorldCom Corporation, dropped dramatically, making them susceptible to the consequences of corporate failure. These may have occurred as a result of their reporting strategy's absence of an integrated foundation. In order to support the reporting style that distorts the majority of corporate failures in Nigerian firms, about 20% of business transactions are actively recorded using a quantitative approach, with the remaining 80% of reports primarily based in an isolated manner in the annual report (Lajorin, 2019).

Human capital is the portion of accounting processes that offer an aspect of evaluation of a firm's operations and activities in conjunction with other capitals (integrated capital). In its reporting system, integrated capital employs financial and non-financial approaches. The present financial reporting system, which pays attention to each component, incorporates all capital sources, including manufactured, social and relationship, financial, human, and natural, into its reporting strategy. This represents a recent change in the fundamentals of accounting from the previous system. Many people have criticised the traditional financial reporting system for its defects. As a result, human capital, a facet of integrated capital, contributed to a clear and trustworthy reporting technique in the company's annual reports. This offers a comprehensive method of decision-making that addresses the shortcomings of the long-standing, biased reporting system. In addition to its primary objective of adding value, integrated capital has a significant impact on profitability. Many of the countries that participated in the International Integrated Reporting Council's (IIRC) pilot programme have adopted this

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concept and its guiding principles. These countries have adjusted their thought processes to conform to a new reporting framework.

The experience of the United States of America with the global financial crisis in the 1990s gave rise to the concept of the International Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF), which was implemented in 2007 and remained in force until 2009. The International Integrated Reporting Framework was introduced because a thriving economy required it due to the growing number of investors in the capital markets and their confidence in financial stability. Nonetheless, the IIRF serves a range of interests in the advancement of corporate reporting in all of its contexts. For as long as it is in use, the International Integrated Reporting Framework will continue to support a number of interests in the advancement of corporate reporting. Nigerian business statutes need integrated reporting. However, integrated reporting is increasingly gaining traction in several African nations, notably Nigeria, because the African Integrated Reporting Committee was established in compliance with the regulations of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria. Furthermore, it is thought that as long as integrated reporting is preserved, a comprehensive wealth-building strategy will be in place. As a result, integrated reporting includes a wide range of information to show how the business generates value both now and in the future.

Although studies and theories conducted in developed countries indicate that information technology boosts firms' value, this assumption could only be confirmed in developing countries following the extensive implementation of integrated reporting. The isolated nature of human capital makes evaluating its benefits potentially problematic. This led the researchers to stress that, even in the face of controversy, valuation is still crucial when taking into account societal needs. The purpose of this study, therefore, is to assess stakeholders' perspectives on human capital and how they influence Nigeria's consumer goods firm's profitability. Although research has been carried out on human capital and performance in Nigeria, none has considered human capital and profitability empirically with a focus on the country's consumer goods firms. This study's primary goal is to ascertain the distinct influence of human capital as well as the profitability represented by return on assets in Nigeria's consumer goods firms.

2. Statement of the Problem

Profitability is still a vital constituent of any successful business. It is possible that improved profitability from the reporting approach in later years rather than in the first year will lead to success in terms of shareholder wealth maximization. Profitability can therefore be determined in the annual report of corporations if all funds utilized in the business are carefully considered in the financial reports of businesses. The absence of human capital from corporate entities' annual reports means that most companies' profitability is still not disclosed. It would have been simpler and easier to evaluate profitability, nevertheless, if the companies' annual reports had taken into account all of the capital (including human capital) at the same time. Financial performance does not seem to be correlated with the amount of capital utilized by a company to create value. The majority of businesses still do not reveal their profitability since human capital, an aspect of sustainable capital, is missing from their yearly reports. Nonetheless, if human capital, in collaboration with all other capitals, had been considered simultaneously in the companies' annual reports, evaluating profitability would have been simpler and easier. There appears to be no connection between a company's profitability and the amount of capital it uses to generate value. Human capital is seen to have a bigger influence on value creation and is a better way to increase a company's profitability, in addition to being a crucial reporting system.

Research from the United States, the Netherlands, Japan, and South Africa, including a study by Ebimobowei and Uche (2021), has established that a company's ability to create value is essential to its ability to remain profitable. To varying degrees of success, studies on the subject have been carried out with a focus on corporate finances and company value. Other studies considered a few human capital variables, like cost of capital, using workable generalised least squares as research tools, and structural capital to examine their influence on business profitability through longitudinal and mixed techniques with firm characteristics. However, despite the use of numerous analytical methods, demographic factors, concepts, and theoretical frameworks, the research's conclusion remains ambiguous. Research on human capital and how it affects profitability in Nigerian consumer goods firms is rare. It has not been stated in the public domain whether human capital has affected the profitability of consumer goods firms in the Nigerian economy. This study considered the influence of humans on the profitability of Nigeria's consumer goods firms, as measured by return on assets.

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Furthermore, the fundamental hypothesis of this research is that human capital has no appreciable influence on the profitability of consumer goods firms. This is further put into the assumption for analytical detail.

Ho₁: There is no significant influence of human capital on the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study focused on consumer goods companies in Nigeria between 2013 and 2022 fiscal years. While return on assets was the proxy for profitability within the relevant years.

3. Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

The interaction between human capital and profitability within the moderation of consumer goods companies can find a reasonable explanation through stakeholder's theory. Stakeholder's theory was revived in the 1980s, but its core concept was first proposed by Mary Parket Folleth about 60 years ago (Schilling, 2000). Any group or individual that can influence or be influenced by the achievement of the organization's goals is considered a stakeholder, according to Freeman (1984). As a result, a stakeholder is any substantial group of individuals or anybody who has a stake in the company, either directly or indirectly (Schilling, 2000). Conversely, direct stakeholders are individuals who have a vested interest in the financial success of the business, including its investors, employees, clients, and suppliers. Indirect stakeholders include the government and society, which are touched by company operations in an indirect manner. Firm objectives affect and are influenced by a variety of parties, including owners, managers, staff, suppliers, payables, receivables, the government, and the general public (Adegbayegun *et al.*, 2020). According to Gray *et al.* (1996), this theory recognises the intricate and dynamic ties that exist between organisations and their stakeholders' relationships that also entail accountability and responsibility. Principles of management and ethics are combined in this worldview. While the management component emphasizes that the firm is more interested in the more powerful stakeholders, the ethical component dictates that all stakeholders be treated equally. Given that they are vital to the company's survival, it will accede to the demands of the influential stakeholders. In order to provide information that fully satisfies the information needs of the many stakeholders, an integrated report must be developed (Adegbayegun *et al.*, 2020). In order to satisfy stakeholders' information needs,

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Camilleri (2018) asserts that human capital must be presented in a detailed manner. Significant stakeholders have the power to affect management choices in ways that are advantageous to the bottom line, society, and the environment.

Similarly, Clarke (2004) suggested that the stakeholder theory viewed organizations as multilateral agreements between a company and its various stakeholders, with the two parties' relationship being governed by rules that have been established over time, both formal and informal. Even if shareholders provide funding for management, they nonetheless depend on staff to perform the business's productive duties. However, the restricted focus on shareholders has broadened to include the interests of various stakeholder groups with respect to ethical, social, and environmental issues (Freeman, 1984; Donaldson and Preston, 1995). Maximising shareholder value is critical since it is the only one that leads to decisions that improve outcomes for all stakeholders, according to Freeman *et al.* (2004). Furthermore, it is impractical to expect managers to identify a broader set of stakeholders and their guiding principles. The stakeholder theory aligns well with the study's aims since it focuses on identifying the elements that support firms' survival and guaranteeing that businesses take into account all interest groups when making decisions using human or intellectual capital, a facet of integrated capital. It contributes to the hypothesis on the impact of a firm's financial features on the human capital of Nigerian consumer goods firms. However, the study supports the stakeholder theory in order to ensure value maximisation and the goals of stakeholders' benefit for the steady profitability of a corporation.

Corporate reporting is an ever-spreading field, as firms continually strive to improve their communication with their stakeholders. One of the most important ways of doing so is through annual human capital, a facet of integrated reporting. Integrated reporting seeks to align relevant information about an organisation's strategy, governance systems, performance, and future prospects in a way that reflects the economic, environmental, and social impact it has on the environment in which it operates. Integrated reporting is primarily aimed at explaining to providers of capital how an organisation creates value over time using these capitals. In contemporary times, integrated reporting encompasses financial, manufactured, human, social, and relational capital in relation to natural capital. It is perceived as an aspect of reporting on the influence of a corporation on the economy and society. Accordingly, financial capital, manufactured capital, human capital, social capital, and relationship capital vis-

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à-vis natural capital are the various forms of integrated capital of a corporation as identified by IIRF (2013), but this study would consider human capital.

Human capital entails people's competencies, capabilities, and experiences and their motivations to innovate, including their alignment with and support for an organisation's governance framework, risk management approach, and ethical values. It also includes their ability to understand, develop, and implement an organisation's strategy, loyalties, and motivations for improving processes, goods and services, including their ability to lead, manage, and collaborate. It involves organisational, knowledge-based intangibles, including intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, software, rights and licences, and organisational capital," such as tacit knowledge, systems, procedures, and protocols.

Management theories have tended to heavily emphasise human capital as non-financial information. It has been found that other intangible capital, such as social and relationship capital, complements it and frequently has an indirect impact on profitability through intricate cause-and-effect linkages (Kaplan and Norton, 2004). In the 1950s and 1960s, economists who saw the link between economic growth, income growth, and the level of labour training first coined the term "human capital." The concept of human capital has gained widespread acceptance in economics literature since Schultz's article, "Investment in Human Capital," appeared in the American Economic Review in 1961. Human capital was handled similarly to physical capital because it was believed that people were a nation's most precious resource. Therefore, in order for human capital to be fully realized, additional forms of capital are required. There must be a willingness on the part of the individual or a particular relationship between the individual and the business for individuals to invest their human capital in the company and for the organisation to benefit (Stiles and Kulvisaechana, 2003). Most people agree that an individual's abilities, as well as the knowledge, expertise, and experience of the company's employees and managers as they apply to the task at hand, have the potential to add to this reservoir of information (Stiles and Kulvisaechana, 2003).

Human capital, according to IIRC (2013), represents the company's employees' skills, knowledge, and alignment with the organisational structure, strategy, and moral principles. In order to maximise the value contributed by the business, managers must

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create a behavioural tool that helps them understand the elements that affect knowledge and human capital (IIRC, 2013). Using the suggested tool, knowledge professionals can better understand how the organisation views intellectual enterprise, knowledge management support systems, processes, and personal value addition, as well as how they view their own performance, innovation, and the effects of leaving, according to Kannan and Akhilesh (2002). The organisation may move employees into higher value-added positions by giving them more chances to share and collect information and by rewarding initiative, collaboration, and invention in addition to learning. Profitability and the added value of human capital can both be improved by increased leader involvement and direction, as well as by top management visibility and support. Since then, there has been a change in the understanding that intangible rather than tangible resources are what create value (Kannan and Akhilesh, 2002).

Human capital was acknowledged as a valuable competitive insubstantial asset by Stiles and Kulvisaechana (2003). Due to the variety of benefits and connections to a wide range of various disciplines, it has been observed that the concept of human capital enters contemporary arguments in a variety of ways, such as health, paid work, and caging. However, leadership is crucial if we want to increase our human and intellectual capital. Human capital is one of the production components that, when stored, can provide additional value, according to Zulkifli *et al.* (2017). As a result, human capital takes into account a person's capacity for converting raw materials into goods and services, as well as the fact that this capacity may be developed through the educational system. Having the capacity to impart their own knowledge and training in order to advance national human capital and education makes human capital's knowledge and skills a result of conscious investment (Zulkifli *et al.*, 2017).

People with access to and ownership of various forms of wellbeing are the embodiment of human capital (Stightz, 2011). The idea of human capital as non-financial information enters a modern debate in a variety of forms due to the payoff range and ties to a variety of different fields. Because it is a catalyst for economic growth and innovation, higher income and reduced poverty, greater access to jobs, and one of the assets that should be preserved and developed alongside natural capital to ensure sustainable development, human capital becomes a key concept in relation to the development of intellectual mechanisms (Stightz, 2011). The future earning potential of an organisation depends on this capital, even though it is the least frequently revealed.

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The future earnings potential of an organisation is largely dependent on investments made in R&D, innovation, human resources, and external relationships, all of which can influence a company's competitive advantages. In order for a company to comprehend and manage its knowledge resources, Guthrie *et al.* (2012) noted that humans are a component of accounting, reporting, and management technology. It requires the development of knowledge resources, including personnel skills, customer relations, financial relationships, communication, and information technology, as an embodiment of accounting. It is crucial to remember that human property and capital are interchangeable terms. The organisation has particular legal rights to preserve the portion of human capital known as human property, such as patents. However, human capital refers to larger knowledge-based intangibles over which a given company may not have distinct legal rights. Another viewpoint on the idea of human capital was provided by Garthorpe (2009). The term "human capital" is deficient since it emphasises only a portion of human property while downplaying its detrimental elements, such as liabilities and contingent human property duties. In addition, current classification techniques do not take unethical behaviour into account, though socially conscious investors would find such an ethical classification valuable. The European Commission received in-depth viewpoints on the concept of human capital from the high-level expert group on RICARDIS (2006). One of these is the fact that human capital is a key factor in a business's future earning potential, with a close connection and dependability between investment in research and development, innovation, human resources, and external relationships, which can determine the competitive edge of the organisation. In this study, human capital is measured by the actual value of the investment in personnel costs of the firm. The study preferred the return on assets as its profitability indicator because it takes into consideration all the resources that go into producing a company's return. The return on assets metric, which was taken into consideration in the study as a measure of profitability, is described below.

Return on assets is the total revenue generated by each asset that a company has invested in for its daily operations. It displays the ratio of a company's earnings to its available capital (Suresh, 2018). By dividing income before interest and taxes by the total asset value of a business, Ewereoke (2018) computed the return on assets. Since it is thought that management has little control over taxes, the return on assets should be

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calculated using profit before taxes. Conversely, a rising return on assets indicates that a company is performing better. Return on assets can be used to compare businesses of a similar kind within and between companies, even though it is a precise indicator of a company's total financial health over a certain time period. Although there are numerous methods to evaluate a company's performance, the return on assets, which is determined by dividing the annual earnings or profit by the total assets of Nigerian firms, was employed in this study.

Pamungkas and Meini (2023) investigated the effects of sustainability reporting and intellectual capital disclosure on firm value, with profitability serving as a moderator. According to the report, as Indonesia's economy grew, all businesses were forced to raise their game in order to meet their objectives. In addition, it was anticipated that the company would boost its worth for the benefit of its stockholders. The research's objective was to demonstrate empirically how intellectual capital and sustainability reporting affect corporate value. The research was innovative in that it attempted to determine whether profitability could reduce the impact of intellectual capital disclosure and sustainability reporting on firm value. An *ex-post facto* research design with multiple regression analysis was adopted in the research. The research used panel data from 32 manufacturing firms listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2017 to 2021. Data processing was done with Warp PLS 8.0. The results showed that disclosure of sustainability reporting has a negative effect on firms' value, whereas intellectual capital has a positive effect on them. Profitability was meant to strengthen the relationship between disclosure of sustainability reporting and intellectual capital on firm value.

Baridoo *et al.* (2023) examined the human capital reporting and market capitalization of pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. The purpose of the research was to determine how, over a ten-year period from 2012 to 2021, quoted pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria's stock market performed in respect to their human capital reporting. The annual reports and accounts of seven (7) pharmaceutical businesses listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group Plc were used to gather secondary data for the research using a purposeful sampling strategy. In the research, an *ex-post facto* research design was used. With the aid of E-View version 10, statistical tools such as ordinary least squares and multiple linear regressions were employed to examine the data. The salaries and wages of employees, the cost of retirement benefits, and other employee costs

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served as stand-ins for the independent variable, human capital reporting, while the earnings per share indicator of market capitalization served as the dependent variable. The variables were shown to be stationary at the first difference by the stationarity test. A long-term link was established through the co-integration test. In testing the hypotheses, the independent variables, which were represented by reporting employee salaries and wages, reporting the cost of retirement benefits, and reporting other employee costs, were statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. The Granger causality test demonstrated that there was no causal relationship between the variables. According to the research, market capitalization is measured by earnings per share and human capital reporting. It was advised that adequate reporting and suitable compensation plans be created to promote the hiring, retaining, and motivation of priceless, distinctive, inimitable, and well-organised human assets who have the greatest potential to influence the performance of pharmaceutical companies on the stock market.

Amos and Oboh (2023) evaluated human capital reporting and firms' stock market performance: A study of the services sector of the Nigerian exchange. The research was intended to examine the impact of human capital reporting on the stock market performance of listed firms in the Nigerian services sector between 2016 and 2020. As of February 2022, there were twenty-four (24) publicly traded companies in Nigeria's services sector. Based on the availability of their annual and sustainability reports for the five-year period under consideration, all but two of the companies listed in the services sector of the Nigerian Exchange Group Plc were chosen. The fixed effects hierarchical regression technique was used to evaluate the data after the fact using an *ex-post facto* research design. It was found that the development of human capital has a positive and significant impact on a company's stock market performance (Adj. $R^2 = 0.856$, $F(4, 108) = 26.66$, $p < 0.05$). However, the researchers found that human capital compensation and welfare reporting had a negative, albeit negligible, impact on businesses' stock markets (Adj. $R^2 = 0.808$, $F(4, 108) = 19.28$, $p < 0.05$). In light of the findings, it was determined that human capital acquisition, training, and development have a positive and significant influence on the stock market performance of firms in Nigeria, whereas human capital remuneration and welfare reporting have a negative but minor influence. The management boards of businesses were advised to reassess their human capital management strategies, particularly in relation to compensation and welfare. To combat irregular reporting patterns among businesses worldwide, local and

international standard-setters were urged to create specific human capital reporting standards, and the Securities and Exchange Commissions were counselled to enforce strict adherence to such standards.

Nweke (2023) investigated human capital development and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria: the role of women education. The study considered how Nigeria's manufacturing industry performed and how human capital was developed between 1990 and 2018. In Nigeria, the success of the manufacturing sector was assessed using the output of the manufacturing industry and the enrollment of female students in secondary and post-secondary institutions. As check variables, other variables like the percentage of women in the labour force, the life expectancy of women, and bank lending to the manufacturing sector were employed. The Central Bank of Nigeria's annual statistical bulletin for 2018, the Central Bank of Nigeria's annual report and statements of accounts for various years, the World Bank's development indicators for various years, journals, online resources, and the International Labour Organisation were among the secondary sources used to gather annual time series data on target variables. The research design chosen was *ex post facto*. The performance of Nigeria's manufacturing industry was estimated using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model, with emphasis on the contribution of women's education. The output of the manufacturing sector was shown to be positively and significantly impacted by women's education in the short term, according to the findings of the ARDL estimations. Additionally, women's education has a favourable long-term effect on the production of the industrial sector. It was suggested that incentives be increased to attract more females to pursue education, especially up to the tertiary level, given that female education, particularly up to that level, boosts the output of the manufacturing sector. To provide women with equal opportunities, gender equality has been the major concern in the research.

5. Methodology

An *ex-post facto* design was adopted for this study. This design permits the use of historical human and intellectual capital and profitability data for the ascertainment of its influence. The entire population of 21 consumer goods firms was the subject of this research. However, a sample size of 17 companies in this sector was obtained from the population using purposive sampling technique. Moreover, the researchers relied on

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secondary sources of data for this study, and data were obtained through the annual report from 2013 to 2022. In testing the influence of human capital on the profitability of the sector, a simple econometric model was utilised, and the formula was stated as follows:

$$Y=f(x) \quad \text{Equation 3.1}$$

Where:

Y is the profitability measured by return on assets. X is the human capital (HC). In a functional form, it was stated as; $ROA = f(HC)$

Hypothesis one Substituting profitability and human capital variables in a regression statistics equation, the model was developed thus;

$$ROA_{it} = \Omega_0 + \Omega_1(HC)_{it} + e_{it} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where: ROA	=	Return on Assets
Ω_0, ξ_0	=	Constant Terms
Ω_1, ξ_1	=	Estimated Coefficients of the independent variables
HC	=	Human Capital
e	=	Error term
i	=	Number of Companies
t	=	Number of years

6. Data Analyses and Findings

The hypothesis was tested through simple regression analysis using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0 at 5% level of significance. However, results were stated as follows:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics
	s	s				ics	cs
						Error	Error
Profitability (ROA) (%)	170	-235.99	617.43	7.5224	57.84140	7.447	.186
Human Capital (N'000)	170	20,160.05	1,338,482.0	8,208,254.01	11,178,469.170	1.919	.186
Valid N (listwise)	170	0	0	18	41	3.208	.370

Source: *Researcher's Computation (2024)*

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. Profitability, which was proxied by return on assets, was the dependent variable in the study. From table 4.1, the return on assets has a minimum of -235.99% and a maximum of 617.43%. Also, there was a mean of 7.5224% with a standard deviation of 57.84140% of profitability. This signifies that the mean and standard deviation rate deviated by 50.319%. However, the coefficient of skewness of 7.447% implies that the data is positively skewed and meets the symmetrical or normal distribution of the data set and is tilted towards the right tail of the distribution, hence leptokurtic, as the kurtosis value stood at 80.110% but was visualised to be highly peaking with a thin bell and a heavy tail and meeting the acceptable criteria.

The human capital was represented by personnel costs in the study. Table 4.1 indicates that the minimum and maximum values of human capital (personnel costs) were N20,160.00 and N1,338,482.00, respectively, with a mean value of N8,208,254.0118 and a standard deviation of N11,178,469.17041. This shows a dispersion of the mean and standard deviation of personnel costs. The coefficient of skewness of 1.919 implies that personnel costs are positively skewed, and the data set meets the symmetrical distribution and is tilted towards the right tail of the distribution. The kurtosis value of 3.208 suggests that personnel costs are leptokurtic in nature and meet acceptable distribution criteria.

Test of Hypothesis

The research hypothesis was tested in this section. The test was carried out using ordinary least square regression with the model specification shown below, using Statistical Package for Social Science version 20.0 software. The result of the analysis is shown below:

H₀: There is no significant influence between human capital and return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Regression Summary on the influence of HC on ROA of consumer goods companies in Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.520 ^a	.271	.266	.82611	1.525

a. Predictor: (Constant), Human Capital. b. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2024)

Table 4.3: ANOVA Summary on the influence of HC on ROA of consumer goods companies in Nigeria

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	42.553	1	42.553	62.352	.000 ^b
	Residual	114.653	168	.682		
	Total	157.206	169			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability. b. Predictor: (Constant), Human Capital

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2024)

Table 4.4: Regression Coefficient on the influence of HC on ROA of Consumer goods companies in Nigeria

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.809	.453		6.202	.000		
	Human Capital	.557	.071	.520	7.896	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability

2 *FKHU¶\V\$QDO\WLFDO2XWSXW*

Table 4.2 presents a summary of the influence of human capital on the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The R-square of 0.271 indicates that 27.1% of the human capital really contributed to the return on assets of the consumer goods companies in Nigeria and is explained in the regression model. Table 4.3 shows a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was accepted. This implies that there was a significant positive influence of human capital on the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This is in line with the decision rule of the study. This was further confirmed by the t calculated at 7.896 against the critical value of t, which was represented by 1.962. Table 4.4 showed a beta coefficient of 0.520 for human capital, implying that, if other variables are held constant, as human capital increases, return on assets increases, respectively, in that magnitude. A N1 increase in human capital would lead to a N0.520 increase in return on assets.

7. Discussion of the Findings

Inspired by the quest to find out if human capital influences the profitability of consumer goods companies in Nigeria, a hypothesis was developed and analysed. Data for the variables across seventeen consumer goods firms for a period of ten years were computed and analysed, and the results are discussed below:

In line with the hypothesis, human capital, with a t-statistic of 7.896 and a probability value of 0.000 less than 0.05 and a regression coefficient of 0.520, demonstrated a weak positive and significant influence on return on assets. This indicates that human capital has a significant positive influence on the profitability of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The analysis implies that a unit increase in human capital will cause about a N52.00 increase in the return on assets of the sector. This supposes that it is the enterprise viability and assumption in reporting an entity's capital, as businesses are expected to possess the ability to defend their activities for the long term and not be liquidated in the short run. In line with the findings of Amos and Oboh (2023), the research asserted a significant influence of human capital reporting firms' stock market performance of 24 publicly traded companies in Nigeria from 2016 to 2020.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 3, APRIL, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

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8. Conclusion and Recommendations

Drawing from the test results, the researchers concluded that there is a significant positive influence of human capital on the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Therefore, human capital exerts the most significant influence on the return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Therefore, the researchers recommended as follows:

- i. Listed Nigerian consumer goods companies ought to make greater investments in human and intellectual capital through staff training and retraining, as well as human resources management.
- ii. To increase productivity, product quality, and profitability, the company should invest more in digital assets such as artificial intelligence and other specialised software packages.
- iii. Rather than letting listed corporations opt out, regulatory authorities should require them to participate, since human capital continues to be the firm's growth engine.
- iv. Listed companies in Nigeria should be monitored against non-adherence to human capital reporting practices and impose appropriate sanctions on offenders.

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